

THE SOUND OF MUSIC... THERAPY: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

by

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Abstract

The primary purpose of this review was to assess the existing evidence base on musically-based, clinical interventions (MBI) in clinical interventions to treat disorders of consciousness (DOC), chronic/terminal illnesses, and other pain management goals. The secondary aim was to assess access to the method in communities identifying as Black, Indigenous, and People of Color (BIPOC). A systematic literature review was conducted using the database PubMed. MBI in clinical settings were operationally defined by the American Music Therapy Association (AMTA) as the use of music to manage symptoms, improve quality of life (QoL) in patients with chronic health conditions, and promote physical/psychosocial function. This definition was used to inform article inclusion criteria which consisted of articles that were US-based, clinical in setting, and published in the last 20 years (i.e. 2003-2023). Keywords used in the search were limited to music therapy, musically-based interventions, clinical setting, and music. All peer-reviewed, English articles, Randomized Controlled Trials (RCT's), systematic reviews, and meta-analyses were included. Exclusion criteria consisted of articles that were not based in the US or focused on the application of the method on infants. The results of the review indicate the MBI treatment method may have beneficial effects in clinical settings, but there is a gap in access for BIPOC patients. As a result, future research taking this factor into account is necessary.

Keywords: music therapy; musically-based interventions; clinical setting; music

Table of Contents

Methods..... 5

 Definition of Terms 5

Results..... 7

 Disorders of Consciousness 9

 Chronic and Terminal Illnesses..... 10

 Individualized Goals 13

 Musically-based Interventions in BIPOC 15

Discussion..... 16

Conclusion 17

 Implications for Future Research 18

Methods

Definition of Terms

According to the American Music Therapy Association (AMTA), music therapy can be defined as the clinical and evidence-based use of a combination of musically-based interventions to accomplish individualized goals, ranging from pain management to the promotion of physical and mental rehabilitation, within a therapeutic relationship by a credentialed professional who has completed an approved music therapy program (AMTA, n.d.). Elements of this definition are clarified by the AMTA in the following manner:

- Clinical and evidence-based: There is an intrinsic relationship between music therapy research and clinical practice
- Musically-based interventions: The process is “purpose-driven” within a productive use of musical experience based on the AMTA Standards of Clinical Practice
- Individualized goals within a therapeutic relationship: This process includes the assessment, treatment planning, therapeutic intervention, and evaluation of each patient
- Credentialed professional: Each credential or professional designation (i.e.: Music Therapist-Board Certified (MT-BT), Registered Music Therapist (RMT), Certified Music Therapist (CMT)) requires a set of professional competencies to be fulfilled and maintained according to established professional standards
- Approved music therapy program: A degreed program with AMTA approval and the National Association of Schools of Music (NASM) accreditation

Clinical settings can be defined as settings in which the primary purpose is to deliver medical care in a one-on-one provider-patient relationship (The Community Guide, n.d.). Examples of

such settings include private office practices, managed care facilities, or hospitals (The Community Guide, n.d.).

A systematic literature search using PubMed that was informed by the key terms music therapy (MT) and musically-based interventions (MBI), as used by the National Institutes of Health was conducted. It is important to highlight that the term “musically-based interventions” (MBI) is the most ubiquitous term in health literature. For the purpose of this review, the terms “musically-based interventions” (MBI) and “music therapy” (MT) will be used interchangeably. MBI/MT in clinical settings is defined as the use of music to manage symptoms and improve quality of life (QoL) in patients with chronic health conditions and promote physical/psychosocial function (Warth, 2014). This definition was used to inform article inclusion criteria which consisted of health literature that were peer-reviewed, US-based, clinical in setting, and published in the last 20 years (i.e. 2003-2023). All peer reviewed, English articles, Randomized Controlled Trials (RCT’s), systematic reviews, and meta-analyses were included.

The initial search results using the selected keywords or phrases (music therapy, musically-based interventions, clinical setting, and music) yielded over 8,000 results in PubMed. Once the filters for the inclusion criteria were applied, the search yielded 2,564 results. An additional search with the added keyword “clinical” yielded 200 results. Of the 200 results that were filtered for our analysis, 11 articles were selected for this systematic review as they specifically addressed treatment methods to DOC, specialized pain management, and chronic/terminal conditions treated in clinical settings from PubMed.

Thirteen additional academic and non-academic resources were added using Google Scholar as the original 11 articles from PubMed did not provide enough contextual factors for MBI in clinical settings. Two resources from the American Music Therapy Association (AMTA)

that provide the official definition of MBI and list of professional competencies that a music therapist must meet in order to be a board certified music therapist alongside five resources that provide context for the origins of the treatment methods were added (AMTA, 2008; AMTA, n.d.). Two resources that define Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) and clinical settings as utilized throughout this review were also added (PRISMA Statement, n.d.; The Community Guide, n.d.). An additional resource covering an interview of an official board-certified music therapist was included to supplement the understanding of the use of MBI to accomplish individualized goals in clinical settings (CHOC, 2019). Three additional peer-reviewed articles that highlighted gaps in access to the treatment method in communities identifying as Black, Indigenous, People of Color (BIPOC) were also included (Crawford et. al, 2021; Medina, 2021; Williams et. al, 2000). This systematic review thus provides a synthesis of results from 11 PubMed articles and 13 additional resources to supplement the contextual factors of MBI for review.

Results

The 11 initial PubMed articles (Altenmuller et. al, 2013; Davis, 2012; de Dreu et. al, 2012; Geretsegger et. al, 2017; Gramaglia et. al, 2019; Groß et. al, 2010; Leubner et. al, 2017; Raglio et. al, 2016; Rollnik et. al, 2014; Sharon et. al, 2013; Wang et. al, 2020) yielded the following themes: stimulation of cognitive functions and improvement in overall quality of life (QoL) for patients with disorders of consciousness; reductions in anxiety and depression and increased QoL in patients with cancer; improvement in global and mental states, improvement in social functioning, and improved QoL for patients with Schizophrenia; improved QoL, walking ability, and balance for patients with Parkinson's Disease; improved QoL, increased pain

management, and decrease in depressive symptoms in patients with Fibromyalgia; improved QoL in patients with Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS); and improvements in depressive symptoms and overall QoL in patients with individualized, clinical goals. The 13 additional resources provide context to this systematic review (AMTA, 2008; AMTA, n.d.; CHOC, 2019; Crawford, 2021; Davis, 2012; Medina, 2021; Montinari et. al, 2018; PRISMA Statement, n.d.; Srinivasan, 2016; The Community Guide, n.d.; Williams et. al, 2000).

Music exerts a powerful influence on human beings. It represents an enjoyable activity, but its impact goes way beyond simple enjoyment. Music is widely perceived as having healing powers throughout history and is full of examples linking music to physical and mental healing (Montinari et. al, 2018). The earliest known reference to music therapy first appeared in 1789 in an unsigned article titled “Music Physically Considered” in *Columbian Magazine* (AMTA, n.d.). The next, referencing the therapeutic value of music, appeared in two medical dissertations first published by Edwin Atlee and then Samuel Mathews in the early 1800s; both contributors were students of Dr. Benjamin Rush, a physician and psychiatrist who strongly believed in the benefits of using music to treat disease (Srinivasan, 2019). The 1800s also saw one of the first documented interventions of music therapy in an institutional setting on Blackwell’s Island in New York alongside Corning’s use of music to alter dream states during psychotherapy which was the first recorded systematic experiment (Davis, 2012). The implementation of the method in clinical settings began after World War I and II when the efforts of community musicians of all types in Veterans hospitals began to elicit notable physical and emotional responses in the thousands of veterans suffering from both physical and emotional trauma inflicted upon them as a result of the wars (AMTA, n.d.). Since then, the method has been used as a means of treatment

for a range of ailments, including, but not limited to, disorders of consciousness and chronic diseases within the field of medicine.

Disorders of Consciousness

While research is scant, one of the most common clinical uses of music therapy is among patients with disorders of consciousness. Studies suggest that MBI may enhance wellbeing, stimulate cognitive functions, and improve the overall quality of life. For example, in a review article published in the *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, researchers provide an overview of the use of music as a therapeutic method in the rehabilitation of comatose patients and other disorders of consciousness (Rolknik et. al, 2014). Among the vast amounts of research that the authors reviewed, a few key findings stuck out. Neuroimaging studies show that DOC patients may have cortical responses to language stimulation which indicates that listening to familiar sounds may not only induce cognitive functions but also have an impact on emotional processing (Rolknik et. al, 2014). The finding of brain response to emotional stimuli in these patients is of importance due to the fact that levels of awareness cannot be evaluated without first addressing the question of whether these cognitive processes elicit a subjective emotional response (Sharon et. al, 2013). Emotion and consciousness are considered to be inextricably linked as each conscious state is tied to some form of emotion; as a result, emotion is regarded as a key component of one's experience of their environment, including sense of self, deeming it an ever-present fundamental constitute of the quality of human consciousness (Sharon et. al, 2013). It has also been shown that listening to music induces a broad activation of several complex neural networks and elicits emotional processes via the limbic system in alert subjects (Altenmuller et. al, 2013). The activation of these limbic and cortical areas support the hypothesis that these responses could potentially be a sign of an increased awareness. Thus, the researchers deemed it reasonable to

believe that music listening may be a powerful stimulator in the therapy of patients suffering from DOC. However, due to the considerable lack of evidence present to support this belief, the researchers came to the conclusion that further investigation is necessary to merit the therapeutic potential of music therapy in DOC patients (Rolknik et. al, 2014).

Chronic and Terminal Illnesses

Another area in which the clinical use of music therapy is typically applied is for patients with chronic and terminal illnesses. In an article published in the *Critical Reviews in Oncology/Hematology*, authors reviewed 40 studies following the PRISMA statement to summarize the evidence that has been found pertaining to MBI in cancer patients (Gramaglia et. al, 2019). PRISMA is an evidence-based set of items that are used for reporting in systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA Statement, n.d.). This method of analysis is useful because it focuses on evaluating the effects of reported interventions (PRISMA Statement, n.d.). For this specific analysis, the researchers focused on articles that analyzed the impact of music therapy interventions in cancer patients on four main outcomes: anxiety, depression, pain, and quality of life (QoL). The authors found that a positive effect of the MBI interventions on the outcomes that were measured in the study was supported; greater reductions of anxiety and depression were observed in patients with breast cancer (Gramaglia et. al, 2019). An improvement in quality of life (QoL) was also reported by over half (54.5%) of the studies analyzed (Gramaglia et. al, 2019). An association was found between QoL improvement and setting where music therapy intervention was delivered; specifically, improvement in QoL was less common when treatment was administered in hospital wards (Gramaglia et. al, 2019). Overall, the researchers conclude that the studies included in the analysis seem to support a positive effect of music therapy on these main outcomes, which is consistent with previous research suggesting the effectiveness of

musically-based interventions and recommend that future research is conducted in this field due to increasing evidence of music therapy effectiveness, tolerability, and ease of application and use in clinical settings (Gramaglia et. al, 2019).

The use of MBI for Schizophrenia and Parkinson's disease, both chronic illnesses, has become more common in recent years. In a review article published in *Cochrane Library*, a group of review authors independently selected, quality assessed, and data extracted studies that compared music therapy with standard care, placebo therapy, and no treatment (Geretsegger et. al, 2017). 18 studies, with a total of 1215 participants, were included in the review. A positive effect on an individual's global state was found for patients that received music therapy in comparison to standard care (Geretsegger et. al, 2017). Medium-term continuous data identified good effects of music therapy on patients' negative symptoms using the Scale for the Assessment of Negative symptoms (Geretsegger et. al, 2017). These findings suggest that the addition of music therapy to standard care has the potential to improve the global and mental states alongside the social functioning and quality of life of patients with chronic brain disorders. Similarly, other research shows that MBI has the potential to serve as a promising intervention to improve gait and gait-related activities in patients with Parkinson's disease (de Dreu et. al, 2012). In an article published in *Parkinsonism & Related Disorders*, a group of researchers conduct a meta-analysis of the effects of musically-based interventions on walking ability, balance, and the overall quality of life of patients with Parkinson's disease. A sensitivity analysis on two different types of MBI revealed significant improvements in walking velocity for gait-related MBI, but not for dance related MBI (Geretsegger et. al, 2017). The researchers came to the conclusion that MBI seems to be a promising method that can be used for the improvement of gait and gait-related activities for chronic illnesses like Parkinson's.

In more recent years, musically-based interventions have been applied to fibromyalgia. The condition is a complex and non-articular rheumatism that causes pain and tenderness throughout the body, as well as fatigue and difficulties with sleep (Wang, 2020). The cause of the chronic condition is not fully understood by scientists, but research suggests that music therapy can help to alleviate the pain symptoms patients with fibromyalgia experience and improve overall QoL. In a review article published in *Explore*, Wang et. al (2020) evaluated the effects of music therapy on pain, depression, and quality of life in patients with fibromyalgia. The review consisted of seven randomized controlled trials. The Pain Visual Analog Scale, McGill Pain Scale, Beck Depression Scale, and Fibromyalgia Impact Questionnaire were used as outcome measures. The author's evidence indicated that patient's utilizing music therapy interventions had lower scores on the Pain Visual Analog Scale (95% confidence interval [CI] - 2.22 to -1.18, $Z= 6.44$, $P < 0.00001$, four studies) and Beck Depression Scale (95% CI -0.65 to -0.33, $Z= 2.17$, $P= 0.03$, two studies) (Wang et. al, 2020). Significant differences were not observed on the McGill Pain Scale between the music intervention and control groups (95% CI -0.83 to -0.09, $Z= 1.59$, $P=0.11$) (Wang et. al, 2020). The Fibromyalgia Impact Questionnaire elicited a general qualitative description due to high heterogeneity ($I^2= 96\%$, $P < 0.00001$) (Wang et. al, 2020). The researchers came to the conclusion that music therapy is superior to non-music therapy in the treatment of pain, depression, and overall QoL of fibromyalgia patients in clinical settings. However, due to the low quantity of studies included in the search, further research is necessary to further confirm the beneficial effects of the treatment method.

Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, more commonly known as ALS, is another terminal illness in which music therapy methods are applied. ALS is a rare neurological disease that affects motor neurons which subsequently impair control of voluntary muscles (Ragaglio et. al, 2016).

The causes of ALS are unknown at present, but research suggests that the application of this method may have a positive impact on the overall QoL for patients with the condition. Raglio et. al (2016) conducted a randomized controlled study that assessed the efficacy of active music therapy (AMT) on anxiety, depression, and QoL in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. Thirty patients were randomly assigned to experimental [AMT alongside standard of care (SC)] or control (SC) groups; AMT consisted of 12 sessions whereas SC treatment was solely based on physical and speech rehabilitation sessions, occupational therapy, and psychological support (Raglio et. al, 2016). ALS Functional Rating Scale-Revised, Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale, McGill Quality of Life Questionnaire, and Music Therapy Rating Scale were administered to assess outcomes (Raglio et. al, 2016). The results highlighted a significant improvement in McGill Quality of Life Questionnaire global scores ($P=0.035$) for individuals in the AMT group alongside a positive trend in nonverbal and sonorous-music relationship during treatment (Raglio et. al, 2016). The researchers came to the conclusion that further studies involving larger samples and a longer duration of AMT intervention are needed to further confirm the effectiveness of the approach in ALS.

Individualized Goals

The American Music Therapy Association defines music therapy as the clinical and evidence-based use of music interventions to accomplish individualized goals (AMTA, n.d.). These goals can range from needing to reduce stress to wanting to regulate mood and improve self-expression. These goals are accomplished within a therapeutic relationship between a credentialed professional that has completed an approved music therapy program and a patient (CHOC, 2019). In essence, evidence-based, musical interventions are used as the tool which helps support patients' non-musical needs or goals. The types of musically-based interventions

that are used for treatment are entirely dependent upon the patients' clinical goal. Kevin Budd, a board-certified music therapist in CHOC's Mental Health Inpatient Center, posits an example of a patient with a clinical goal of increasing identification of positive coping skills. Budd explains that a lyric analysis within the patient's preferred style of song, a rewrite of the chorus that includes identification of a negative situation and positive coping skills to help address it, and having the patient share their creation via singing or spoken word would all be used in combination to achieve the patient's non-musical need (CHOC, 2019). This use of assessment, treatment planning, and evaluation by music therapists to ensure a patient's current methods of music therapy meet their treatment goals is being explored by researchers.

Research suggests that the application of musically-based interventions may help to address multiple clinical goals and improve overall QoL. Leubner et. al (2017) explored the effectiveness of music interventions in treating depression. A review of original research trials utilizing music therapy as intervention to treat individuals with depressive symptoms was conducted (Leubner et. al, 2017). 28 studies with a total of 1,810 participants met inclusion criteria and were selected. The researchers found there to be improvements in depressive symptoms after music therapy treatments which suggests that the method may be useful for the treatment of depressive symptoms which can be classified as an individualized goal (Leubner et. al, 2017). A pilot study exploring the effects of music therapy in the treatment of children with delayed speech development, another individualized goal, suggests similar results. The observational study consisted of 18 children with delayed speech development that were split into music therapy and non-treatment groups (Groß et. al, 2010). The researchers found that compared to the baseline, there was a positive development in the music therapy group (Groß et. al, 2010). Both phonological capacity and the children's understanding of speech increased under

treatment alongside their cognitive structures, action patterns, and level of intelligence (Groß et al, 2010). These results suggest that music therapy may have a measurable effect on individualized goals, however further studies need to be conducted to investigate the mechanisms of these interactions in greater depth.

Musically-based Interventions in BIPOC

Research on music therapy and other musically-based interventions highlights the method as a potentially effective form of treatment for pain as it significantly enhances neurological, psychological, and social facets of human perception, emotion, and interaction. Its dynamic interventions benefit both individuals and groups due to the fact that it offers a medium through which people with diverse lived experiences can find comfort in connection. Despite this integral role the treatment modality seems to have in treating and managing pain, evidence of its application in communities of color is nearly nonexistent. Specific key-word searches utilizing the phrases music therapy, music therapy BIPOC, music therapy persons of color, music therapy communities of color, and music BIPOC yielded zero results. When the search was extended beyond clinical settings, the lack of results remained consistent. The only materials found were articles that have also identified this gap in access and pushed for recognition and equity in BIPOC communities. These articles highlighted the lack of culturally diverse music being utilized alongside the emphasis of some cultures over others. There were multiple accounts from different musical therapists highlighting the precedence specific, more Westernized music genres took in their music therapy coursework (Medina, 2021; Crawford, 2021)

As with any other ethnic groups, BIPOC individuals experience terminal/chronic illnesses, mental health issues, and other pain management difficulties that music therapy could address; however, access to the treatment method is often inaccessible to these communities due

to issues of socioeconomic status, lack of transportation, lack of knowledge, and other societal and environmental barriers (Williams et. al, 2000). The American Music Therapy Association (AMTA) has a list of professional competencies that a music therapist must meet in order to be a board certified music therapist. Competencies 17.9 and 17.11 under “17. Professional Role/Ethics” state, respectively, “17.9 Demonstrate knowledge of and respect for diverse cultural backgrounds” and “17.11 Demonstrate skill in working with culturally diverse populations” (AMTA, 2008). These competencies show that having knowledge of diverse communities is necessary and important for music therapists, yet, most undergraduate music therapy curricula lack cultural training. Racial, ethnic, and musical representation is a necessary component of music therapy and should be emphasized and encouraged in curricula to not only improve the overall education and cultural competency of musical therapists, but also ensure the ethical treatment of clients from all backgrounds. In essence, the de-focalization of treatment methods rooted in Western traditions will not only lead to a shift in representation of the identities of underrepresented and marginalized individuals but ensure that people will receive the highest quality of care.

Discussion

This systematic review aimed to assess the existing evidence base on clinical MBI to treat disorders of consciousness (DOC), chronic/terminal illnesses, and other pain management goals. The secondary aim was to assess access to the method in communities identifying BIPOC. To do this, a search of the key terms music therapy, musically-based interventions, clinical setting, clinical, and music was conducted. While the results indicate that MBI have promise in the clinical setting, further research is needed to test the effectiveness and access of MBIs in communities of color. This systematic review has its limitations. The lack of prior research

studies pertaining to the application of the treatment method in communities identifying as Black, Indigenous, and People of Color (BIPOC) limited the scope of the analysis. In addition, the use of a systematic review to achieve the aims previously outlined increased the risk of selection bias which potentially had a negative effect on the results and subsequent analysis. For the purposes of this review, only certain criteria were included which also limited the scope of the analysis. In the future, research should aim to identify how barriers BIPOC individuals face in accessing this treatment method can be eliminated, employ a multitude of researchers to conduct a systematic review to reduce the risk of selection bias, and generalize inclusion criteria to all facets of care.

Conclusion

Based on the review of studies for this systematic review, the implementation of musically-based interventions in the field of medicine holds potential for patients with an array of illnesses. In clinical settings, application of the method has been found to potentially lead to improvements in overall quality of life (QoL) in patients with terminal and chronic illnesses such as cancer, Schizophrenia, Parkinson's Disease, Fibromyalgia, and Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS). The use of music therapy has also been deemed to be a powerful stimulator in the therapy of patients suffering from DOC. Research also suggests that the application of musically-based interventions on patients with individualized clinical goals such as treatment of depressive symptoms, improvement of communication, or regulation of mood may help to address multiple clinical goals and improve overall QoL. Unfortunately, access to this treatment method seems to be virtually non-existent among minority groups. In essence, there is a huge gap in access to the method in BIPOC communities and severe inequities in the types of genres of music being offered to those individuals who are able to access the treatment method.

Implications for Future Research

This systematic literature review aimed to assess the existing evidence base on musically-based, clinical interventions to treat disorders of consciousness (DOC), chronic/terminal illnesses, and other pain management goals. The secondary aim was to assess access to the method in communities identifying as Black, Indigenous, and People of Color (BIPOC). In conducting this systematic review, the following themes emerged: stimulation of cognitive functions and improvement in overall quality of life (QoL) for patients with disorders of consciousness; reductions in anxiety and depression and increased QoL in patients with cancer; improvement in global and mental states, improvement in social functioning, and improved QoL for patients with Schizophrenia; improved QoL, walking ability, and balance for patients with Parkinson's Disease; improved QoL, increased pain management, and decrease in depressive symptoms in patients with Fibromyalgia; improved QoL in patients with Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS); and improvements in depressive symptoms and overall QoL in patients with individualized, clinical goals. As discussed previously, the treatment method holds potential for patients in a clinical setting but gaps in access exist for individuals identifying as Black, Indigenous, and People of Color (BIPOC). Highlighting the ever present need to address health equity and access to innovative therapies in BIPOC communities is critical to bridging the gaps in access to equitable healthcare in the US. Thus, future research should aim to identify how the barriers BIPOC individuals face in accessing this treatment method can be eliminated.

References

- Altenmüller, E., and Schlaug, G. (2013). Neurobiological aspects of neurologic music therapy. *Music Med.* 5, 210–216. doi: 10.1177/1943862113505328
- American Music Therapy Association (AMTA). (2008). *American music therapy association: Professional competencies*. <https://www.musictherapy.org/about/competencies/>
- American Music Therapy Association (AMTA). (n.d.). *History of music therapy*. Musictherapy.Org. <https://www.musictherapy.org/about/history/>
- CHOC. (2019). Music therapy in a mental health setting. *CHOC - Children's Health Hub*. <https://health.choc.org/music-therapy-in-a-mental-health-setting/>
- Crawford, Danyele C. (2021). *The Prevalence of Hip Hop Music in Music Therapy Education & Practice*. Theses & Dissertations. 102. <https://digitalcommons.molloy.edu/etd/102>
- Davis, W. C. (2012). The first systematic experimentation in music therapy: The genius of James Leonard Corning. *Journal of Music Therapy*, 49(1), 102–117. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jmt/49.1.102>
- De Dreu, M., Van Der Wilk, A., Poppe, E., Kwakkel, G., & Van Wegen, E. E. H. (2012). Rehabilitation, exercise therapy and music in patients with parkinson's disease: A meta-analysis of the effects of music-based movement therapy on walking ability, balance and

quality of life. *Parkinsonism & Related Disorders*, 18, S114–S119.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/s1353-8020\(11\)70036-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1353-8020(11)70036-0)

Geretsegger, M., Mössler, K., Bieleninik, Ł., Chen, X., Heldal, T. O., & Gold, C. (2017). Music therapy for people with schizophrenia and schizophrenia-like disorders. *The Cochrane Library*, 2017(5). <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd004025.pub4>

Gramaglia, C., Gambaro, E., Vecchi, C., Licandro, D., Raina, G., Pisani, C., Burgio, V., Farruggio, S., Rolla, R., Deantonio, L., Grossini, E., Krenqli, M., & Zeppegno, P. (2019). Outcomes of music therapy interventions in cancer patients—a review of the literature. *Critical Reviews in Oncology Hematology*, 138, 241–254.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.critrevonc.2019.04.004>

Groß, W., Linden, U., & Ostermann, T. (2010b). Effects of music therapy in the treatment of children with delayed speech development - results of a pilot study. *BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6882-10-39>

Leubner, D., & Hinterberger, T. (2017). Reviewing the effectiveness of music interventions in treating depression. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.01109>

Medina, Eden M. (2021). *Racial and ethnic representation in music therapy education*. Theses & Dissertations. 109. <https://digitalcommons.molloy.edu/etd/109>

Montinari, M. R., Giardina, S., Minelli, P., & Minelli, S. (2018). History of music therapy and its contemporary applications in cardiovascular diseases. *Southern Medical Journal*, *111*(2), 98–102. <https://doi.org/10.14423/smj.0000000000000765>

PRISMA Statement. (n.d.). *PRISMA*. Prisma-Statement.Org. <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

Raglio, A., Giovanazzi, E., Pain, D., Baiardi, P., Imbriani, C., Imbriani, M., & Mora, G. (2016b). Active music therapy approach in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis: A randomized-controlled trial. *International Journal of Rehabilitation Research*, *39*(4), 365–367. <https://doi.org/10.1097/mrr.000000000000187>

Rollnik, J. D., & Altenmüller, E. (2014). Music in disorders of consciousness. *Frontiers in neuroscience*, *8*, 190. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2014.00190>

Sharon, H., Pasternak, Y., Simon, E. B., Gruberger, M., Giladi, N., Krimchanski, B. Z., Hassin, D., & Hendler, T. (2013). Emotional processing of personally familiar faces in the vegetative state. *PLOS ONE*, *8*(9), e74711. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0074711>

Srinivasan, V. A. (2016). Indian classical music: an objective sluice in the realms of mind - body medicine. *Annals of SBV*, *5*(2), 41–45. <https://doi.org/10.5005/jp-journals-10085-5212>

The Community Guide. (n.d.). *Glossary: Definition of terms.*

<https://www.thecommunityguide.org/pages/glossary.html#:~:text=Clinical%20Setting%20%E2%80%93%20Setting%20in%20which,%20Done%20provider%20patient%20relationship>

Wang, M., Yi, G., Gao, H., Wu, B., & Yuexia, Z. (2020). Music-based interventions to improve fibromyalgia syndrome: A meta-analysis. *Explore-the Journal of Science and Healing*, *16*(6), 357–362. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.explore.2020.05.012>

Warth, M., Kessler, J., Koenig, J., Wormit, A. F., Hillecke, T. K., & Bardenheuer, H. J. (2014). Music therapy to promote psychological and physiological relaxation in palliative care patients: Protocol of a randomized controlled trial. *BMC Palliative Care*, *13*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-684x-13-60>

Williams, D. R., & Rucker, T. D. (2000). Understanding and addressing racial disparities in health care. *Health care financing review*, *21*(4), 75–90.